

Selectivity of ClO_4^- , SCN^- , I^- and NO_3^- on Strong Base Exchanger Dowex 1-X4 (Cl^-) in Water-Formamide Media

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EXTENSIVE studies have been made to understand some fundamental characteristics of ion-exchange equilibria in aqueous solutions and reviewed from time to time. Making use of the profound influence of water miscible organic solvents and their use in improving the resolution and speed of separation, many workers have investigated the ion exchange equilibria in organic solvent-water mixtures for a better understanding of the process.

Systematic studies of simple anions in mixed solvent media are sparse. Following the work of Diamond *et al*¹, Bhat² and Narke³, the thermodynamic exchange equilibria among simple inorganic anions in water-formamide medium was investigated with a view to learn the influence of protic water soluble formamide. All the exchange studies were made with chloride form of the resin as a frame of reference and monovalent ions as the counter ions. The observed selectivities of anions in aqueous and water-formamide media are analysed and discussed on the basis of water structure enforced ion pair formation as well as solvation energy concepts as applied to ion exchange equilibria

The selectivities have often been studied with water-organic solvent mixture with dielectric constant of organic solvents less than that of water, giving always an effective dielectric constant of the mixture less than that of water. Formamide with dielectric constant 109, dipole moment 3.68 D and capable of forming hydrogen bond, becomes a good choice.

Experimental

Ion-exchange resin: Air dried strongly basic anion exchanger Dowex 1-X4 (50-100 mesh) was used in chloride form. Its capacity was found to be 3.4 meq/g.

Reagents and solutions: All reagents used were of A.R. grade. A.R. grade formamide was further distilled under reduced pressure (10-15 mm). 0.05 M solutions of the salts were prepared in water and water-formamide mixtures and standardised before use.

Determination of the ions: In the case of ClO_4^- - Cl^- and NO_3^- - Cl^- systems the chloride content of the aliquot was estimated by Volhard's method. In I^- - Cl^- and SCN^- - Cl^- systems iodide and thiocyanate were determined by titration with standard potassium iodate solution.

Determination of selectivity coefficient: The equilibrium studies were carried out in glass stoppered flasks (100 ml) with 0.25 g of the resin and 30 ml of total volume and 0.05 M ionic strength in aqueous and aqueous-formamide (20, 40, 70 and 80% w/w) solutions. Batches were equilibrated by shaking in a thermostat for 6 hr and each solution was then analysed for Cl^- , SCN^- and I^- ions.

Results and Discussion

Considering the ion exchange reaction

as a thermodynamic equilibrium, one can write the following expression for the averaged and corrected selectivity coefficient K_{ax}^{yy} after Gaines and Thomas⁴, Ghate *et al*⁵ and Gupta⁶:

$$\log K_{ax}^{yy} = \int_0^1 \log K_{ax}^{yy} d\bar{N}R_y + 2 \log (f \pm Mx/f \pm My) \quad \dots (2)$$

In formamide-water mixed solvent, equation (2) is modified to take account of the change of the solvent nature. It can be represented by

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_{ax}^{yy} &= \int_0^1 \log K_{ax}^{yy} d\bar{N}R_y + 2 \log (f \pm Mx/f \pm My) \\ &\quad + \log Q \\ &= \log K_{ax}^{yy} + \log Q' \end{aligned} \quad \dots (3)$$

where Q' involves solvent activity terms and activity coefficient corrections for the difference in the standard states of the resin and the external solution phase. The first term on the right hand side of equation (3) was computed as for an aqueous medium; for the second term, the activity coefficient ratio of the two counter ions in formamide-water medium was taken as equivalent to the one in aqueous medium as per Harned's⁷ second rule. Due to paucity of data, the value of Q' was not evaluated. The averaged and corrected selectivity coefficients ($\log K_{ax}^{yy}$) in formamide-water media thus computed are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—AVERAGED AND CORRECTED SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS K_{ax}^{yy} WITH FORMAMIDE CONCENTRATION

Formamide (%w/w)	$\text{ClO}_4^-/\text{Cl}^-$	SCN^-/Cl^-	I^-/Cl^-	$\text{NO}_3^-/\text{Cl}^-$
0	1.77	1.15	0.95	0.56
20	1.37	1.01	0.75	0.84
40	1.20	0.62	0.32	0.62
70	1.23	0.26	0.32	0.73
80	0.94	0.29	-0.08	1.05

In aqueous medium the order of selectivity observed is $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{SCN}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{NO}_3^-$. This is the order expected from their crystallographic radii and data in literature⁸ and also in agreement with the models proposed by Diamond⁹ and Reichenberg¹⁰.

Selectivity order can also be known by free energy data. In the present case, from the available free energy data it is in good agreement qualitatively and the change in standard free energy values as calculated in accordance with the equation

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$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{a,2}^{\text{H}^+}$ show the same selectivity order i.e., $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{SCN}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{NO}_3^-$.

TABLE 2—STANDARD FREE ENERGY CHANGE OF AN ION EXCHANGE REACTION

Anion	$\Delta G_{a,2}^{\text{H}^+}$ k cal mole ⁻¹
ClO_4^-	-2.45
SCN^-	-1.59
I^-	-1.312
NO_3^-	-0.77

One can thus say that Diamond's water structure enforced ion pairing and Reichenberg's hydration free energy concepts are complementary to each other.

Most of the observed phenomena can be explained by the effects of the organic solvent on the structure of water and by the preferential ion-solvation effects. On adding formamide, the external solution becomes a poorer and poorer solvating medium because of the continuous breaking up of the water structure. Though formamide is protic it will not form long chain hydrogen bonding with increased formamide content and it strongly competes with water for ion-solvent interactions and both these effects may result in the reduction of selectivity of the preferred ion. The values in Table 1 show the reduction in $K_{a,2}^{\text{H}^+}$ with increase in formamide content of the ions studied except in the case of NO_3^- - Cl^- exchange where it exhibits an anomalous behaviour which may be due to its size, shape and also may be due to the weak electrolyte nature of nitric acid compared to others in the series. Bhat³ and Ramanathan *et al*^{1,2} have already reported increase in the selectivity of NO_3^- at 70% and above methanol content on weak and strong base exchangers.

The reduction in selectivity of preferred ion (bigger anion) with the increase in the formamide content can be explained as follows.

The partial replacement of water in an aqueous solution by dipolar, protic bigger dipoles of formamide has the following effect on the above system. Though protic, it too breaks the structure of water resulting in the increase of free energy of the system. But the larger anions of lower charge density get solvated by the formamide molecules by the ion dipole interactions making the broken water dipoles free to rejoin the structure of water. Thus, the free energy of the system will be reduced more and more with the increase in formamide concentration in the external solution medium. The external solution, therefore, will now prefer the bigger ion resulting in the decrease in the selectivity.

Another interesting point in these selectivity trends is the change in separation ratio of selectivity constants (corrected) with change in solvent composition. These selectivity constants gave less separation for I^- , SCN^- , and ClO_4^- in aqueous solutions (the ratio being 1 : 1.2 : 1.86) as compared to those obtained in mixed systems (1 : 1.93 : 3.7 in 40%)

Thus, mixed solvents can be of much greater utility for planning separation of these ions.

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Further Studies on Electrolytic Reduction of Nitrogen to Ammonia

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OF the various attempts¹ to reduce nitrogen to ammonia under extremely mild conditions, the one cursorily reported by Palit² involves the reduction of dissolved nitrogen near the cathode kept inside a narrow tube covered by a cellophane paper at the bottom during electrolysis of distilled water in a beaker under non-Faradaic conditions^{3,4}. This electrolytic reduction of nitrogen having technological importance and enzymatic significance is worth further study. The present note records a brief endeavour to find out the essential conditions and a plausible mechanism for the occurrence of the unusual phenomenon observed by Palit².

Experimental

To find out the necessary conditions for formation of ammonia by the electrolytic reduction of dissolved nitrogen, the electrolysis is at first carried out in a 1000 ml beaker containing 10^{-3} NH_4SO_4 with platinum foil electrodes (1 cm²) immersed in it, the cathode being kept in a cellophane covered glass tube (16 mm O.D.) containing distilled water (Fig. 1). Current is passed overnight from D. C.